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CompactLight Data Management Plan V.1.3

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On behalf of the CompactLight Partnership

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History of Changes		
Version	Publication Date	Change
1.0	29.06.2018	XLS: Data Management Plan v1.0, 29.06.2018
1.1	05.04.2019	Inserted in the XLS LaTeX Template
1.2	21.12.2019	Overall Update and implementation of EDMS specific information
1.3	31.12.2021	Overall Update and implementation of Zenodo specific information

1 Introduction

This document is based on the Horizon 2020 DMP template, which is designed to be applicable to any Horizon 2020 project that produces, collects or processes research data. It is envisaged to develop a single DMP for the CompactLight project to cover its overall approach.

Link to instructions and template:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan-annotated_en.pdf

1.1 FAIR Data Management

In general terms, the CompactLight research data should be **FAIR**, that is **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**e-usable. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation-solution.

This document is not intended as a strict technical implementation of the FAIR principle; it is rather inspired by FAIR as a general concept.

1.2 Structure of the DMP

The document is a set of statements with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

The DMP is intended to be a living document, in which information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur.

Therefore, the DMP of CompactLight has a clear version number and includes a timetable for updates: As a minimum, it is planned to update the DMP in the context of the Annual Review Meetings of the project. The current update 3 of the document coincides with the end of the project, but since the CompactLight data and documents will be further used by the partners, updates will also be made in the future, if required.

2 Data Summary

The purpose of the CompactLight data management is to gather and preserve all the information produced by the XLS collaboration documenting the performed work and its results. These data may be “open” or “restricted” according to their nature and the intended internal exploitation and reuse by the partners themselves. Critical data for the partners’ follow-up activities, for instance already ongoing or planned projects, are currently defined as “restricted”, while all other data are “open” data. Besides the scientific data, the data management activity concerns also major administrative project data, in order to enable coherent and fully documented records on the preparation of the Conceptual Design Report (CDR). All the “open data” of

the project can be used immediately by other researchers and hence promote the dissemination and exploitation of the respective results for the benefit of the scientific society. The currently "restricted" project data can be used by external researchers through collaboration projects with the project partners and any interested party is explicitly encouraged to contact the project team to discuss their ideas. Also, data classified as "restricted" today can become "open" during the next years and will then be available for use by any interested party in the project's repositories.

Data type and Formats. The CompactLight includes scientific and administrative data of the following types:

The Scientific Data are:

- Calculations
- Simulations
- Measurements
- Designs
- Software
- Presentations
- Reports
- Documents

The Administrative Data are:

- Budget issues
- Transfer Technology issues
- Backup security & data protection
- Access to the data

Re-use of existing data and their origin. Any existing data from the literature re-used during the work is cast into the CompactLight working data formats, e.g. previous designs and measurement data have been reused as references to the CompactLight design and development processes, with indication of original authorship where appropriate. Most of the work that the collaborators have conducted is however in their field of previous expertise and work. Hence, most of the data comes from the scientific and engineering work carried out previously and currently in the frame of the XLS collaboration. Information on the very few background IPRs owned by the partners is provided in deliverable D7.2.

Expected size of the data. It is expected that there will be no extremely big sized data sets, considering that the largest data sets will be the engineering design data. The total volume of centrally administered and archived data is estimated lower than 1 TB.

Potential Users ('data utility'). It is assumed that the data of the CompactLight collaboration can be extremely useful for research institutions and funding agencies aiming to build affordable and sustainable X-Free Electron Lasers of the HX and SX type as well as small ICS sources for different applications, based on an innovative and alternative way of electron acceleration, developed from the CLIC technology. The ultimate deliverable, the CompactLight CDR and its related data, will offer novel and innovative XFEL designs with compact, low-sized accelerators as well as low construction and operation cost. The data are also required for the further development activities that need to be done before such sources can be built.

For the major types of currently "open" CompactLight data, please see the open data tables in section 8.

3 FAIR Data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Repository for all CompactLight data and documents: CERN EDMS

As its main repository for all data, CompactLight is using CERN's Engineering & Equipment Data Management Service (EDMS), which is the main Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) system and Enterprise Asset Management system at CERN. More details on how CERN is using this system, features and tutorials can be found under <https://edms-service.web.cern.ch/>.

EDMS enforces unique identifying numbers. The system allows for direct search of the respective EDMS numbers as well as any query containing author, keyword, creation date range. Additionally, documents in EDMS are attached to (multiple) hierarchical projects. Individual documents can hence be found also through simple navigation of the relevant projects and nodes.

For official deliverables, documentation and publications, CompactLight is following the naming convention of e.g. "XLS-D1.2-DMP". Documents will hence be identified with project name, deliverable number and document name. For all science related documents, we do not follow a particular naming convention.

The project does not intend to use specific search keywords for optimizing possibilities for re-use of The CompactLight data. Modern information technology archive and query systems allow for such vast and flexible searches, that the model of "keywords" is considered being outdated.

The project data storage and archiving system EDMS has an in-build function of versioning, visually displaying all previous states of documents and allowing only the current one to be altered. For documents for which we specifically have multiple updated versions planned, e.g. DMP, we explicitly add version numbers in the documents themselves. The project is documenting any information available and necessary in order to be able to recreate the entire design process. One example is simulation output data which is complemented with simulation code documentation as well as input parameters and tools/functions used. Specifically, for the numerical simulations for which tailored computer codes are being used we use CERN's

GitLab environment with all its Git features and possibilities. For all more standard data sets, e.g. engineering design and cost analysis, EDMS allows for an exhaustive set of predefined information fields where useful meta data information can/must be attributed to the respective documents directly.

3.1.2 Repository for CompactLight open data and documents: Zenodo

As a supplementary repository for the CompactLight open data, the project has selected Zenodo at <https://www.zenodo.org/>. Zenodo, which has been developed by CERN and is funded by CERN, OpenAIRE and the European Commission, aims at promoting Open Science in Europe and worldwide. For this purpose, the platform offers many tools, features and resources that facilitate the sharing, curation and publication of all kinds of FAIR research data, which may be open, closed or restricted. Zenodo accepts all types of digital artefacts, software, and materials associated with the conferences, projects or institutions and does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence. Research published in Zenodo is citable and integrated through OpenAIRE into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission, and citation information is passed to DataCite and onto the scholarly aggregators. (see: <https://about.zenodo.org/>). According to their own assessment, the platform satisfies all mandatory and strongly recommended additional criteria of Plan S for Open Access Repositories, as published in October 2019 (see: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>; <https://www.coalition-s.org/addendum-to-the-coalition-s-guidance-on-the-implementation-of-plan-s/principles-and-implementation/>).

In order to make the CompactLight data findable, a Zenodo Community with the name "CompactLight" (see: <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/compactlight/?page=1&size=20>) has been created and all the open data of the project that have already been uploaded to Zenodo have been included in this Community. From the main page of Zenodo, a search for 'CompactLight' leads to the CompactLight Community and produces a list of all available data files associated with the project. A further search within the CompactLight list is then possible to find a specific item.

All CompactLight data in Zenodo have their own DOI and meta data (CC0 license) that provide an abstract and keywords and inform about the title, version number (with a new DOI for a new version), authors (with ORCID id where available), data type, publication date, upload date, publication journal or conference, associated project names, associated funding, associated license, and others. Citation information and the number of received citations are also indicated. The Zenodo metadata are compliant with OpenAIRE.

Currently the Community contains all published scientific papers, all accepted deliverables, a number of presentations, and a few other open materials of CompactLight. The contents will be further updated with the last deliverables (after acceptance by the Commission), scientific papers published after the end of the project, further presentations, information on CompactLight events and other project data made open in the future.

3.2 Making data openly accessible

In the CompactLight project, scientific and technical data can be open or kept confidential for exploitation according to the provisions of Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. All the scientific and technical data, which are not critical for the exploitation purposes of the project partners, will be openly available once finalized, such as technical specifications or simulation results. Snapshots of various developments and data sets will be published in international scientific journals or presented in international conferences and published in their proceedings.

Most of the Administrative Data are sensitive and cannot be openly available, i.e. detailed financial data concerning the budget of each participating institution and information on the involved human resources. This restriction is derived from the internal rules and regulations applied by each institution in those matters, as well as from current European law. These data are kept closed by each single partner and not inserted in any form in the two repositories.

The CompactLight open data will be accessible through both, the CERN hosted EDMS system and Zenodo (as described above). In both cases, the services are web-based, no specific software tools are necessary and access is available from all over the world. The EDMS system allows for direct queries or browsing through hierarchical structures in order to find the desired data set or information. The search process in Zenodo has been described above.

In Zenodo, a preview and online consultation of the whole document is also possible. The documents can also be exported directly in different platforms: BibTeX, CSL, DataCite, Dublin Core, DCAT, JSON, JSON-LD, GeoJSON, MARCXML, and Mendeley.

There is an extensive guide on how to use EDMS readily available at CERN under <https://edms-service.web.cern.ch/edms-service/faq/EDMS/pages/tutorials.html>. Zenodo offers a comprehensive "Help" section with a short introduction of the features, frequently asked questions and a guide as well as the possibility to contact them directly with a message describing the encountered problem, including attachments (see: <https://help.zenodo.org/>). There is also a Blog with explanations and informations about the platform (see: <https://blog.zenodo.org/>). The CERN hosted EDMS system is free to use for CERN related activities (XLS qualifies for this criteria through the role of being a partner of the project) and the XLS data will be saved, archived and backed up according to CERN standard procedures along with all the rest of the CERN engineering data. Also for the use of Zenodo a user account is required, for which the subscription is open and free of charge.

There will be no restrictions for access to the CompactLight open data, neither in EDMS nor in Zenodo. After locating the data, both repositories allow for a direct download of the open documents. For this purpose, the Zenodo metadata include information about the file format and file size.

As for the sensitive data, stored currently exclusively in EDMS, access can be granted through the CERN implementation of e-groups on request and with permission by the concerned owners of the data. Potential users of the data can obtain access rights through acquiring a CERN light weight computer account and being added to the relevant e-group, for instance if involved in a follow-up project. For the duration of the project, the access rights for externals has been granted in this way by the project coordinator on a on-demand case and this procedure has

proven to be efficient and reliable.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Most of the scientific and administrative open data will be cast in the form of reports or publications, hence usable with any office productivity suite. Raw data of measurements (where applicable) or simulation output will be stored in plain text, ascii file format or similar, containing headers for data type identification. Hence special software will be necessary for performing post-project analysis. If requested, specifically developed computer codes can be provided for cross checking of results.

The project uses mainly vocabulary and expressions common in the light source as well as accelerator communities where CompactLight as a project is situated and where its partners are coming from.

3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The openly available scientific data produced by CompactLight will be accessible immediately after publication and usable by external parties based on copyright licenses, which are usually CC-BY, but might also be different in the case of publications through science publishers. For instance, in some cases only the "Author Accepted Manuscripts" (AAM) of a publication are openly accessible and have been uploaded in Zenodo. Before using the data, the corresponding provisions should therefore be verified by the user. Some of the more sensitive data, such as for instance company information for the cost analysis, cost data or schedule estimations, will be freely accessible on request after the end of the project. Access to the data in EDMS and the maintenance of the full data set will be ensured according to the data policy of CERN. The open data in Zenodo will be continuously updated by the Coordinator, supported by the project partners, also after the end of the project. It is also planned to link, as far as possible, the open data of the follow-up projects to the CompactLight Community in Zenodo, in order to facilitate the dissemination of information about further developments and application projects of the CompactLight technologies and make it easier for future users to find these data. For this reason, also the CompactLight website will still be maintained and updated with new relevant information for some years.

4 Allocation of Resources

The use of EDMS within the context of CompactLight is free of any cost for the project and, as mentioned above, long term preservation of the data in EDMS will be provided according to CERN methods and practices. The long term preservation of the CompactLight data in Zenodo as well as the use of the data and all offered platform instruments by the users is also free of charge. The insertion of further open project data in Zenodo, the maintenance of the CompactLight Community on the platform, and the update of the project website in the coming years will require work efforts that will be covered by own resources of the Coordinator.

5 Data Security

The data security process for EDMS is split into two concepts. Security with respect to the storage media will be achieved through multi-type backup repositories implemented and handled by CERN's EDMS system, while data security with respect to data handling by users will be ensured through selected access rights for limited to reading and downloading data sets without the possibility of changing / manipulating / saving them in the repository. Also the data archived in Zenodo are stored in the CERN Data Centre that provides the best possible security provisions concerning the location itself as well as the servers, network, data, applications and involved staff (see: <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>).

6 Ethical Aspects

The CompactLight team does not expect any ethical or legal issue related to sharing the open data of the project. It will be ensured that the open data sets shared and preserved on the long term will not contain any personal data or other sensitive information, except for author names, contact data or other information expressively agreed with the concerned persons.

7 Other Issues

It is not foreseen to use any other national / funder /sectorial / departmental procedures for our data management.

8 Open Data tables

1. Deliverable D1.1	
Type	Website
Format	Website
Description	CompactLight website with information about the project, partners, events, documents, and related future activities
Sharing	Public (PU)
Owners	CompactLight project partners
License	CC-BY
Reuse	The project partners will keep the website active in order to communicate with the community and inform about future events, follow-up projects, new developments and everything else concerning CompactLight technologies and infrastructures
Archiving	Not applicable
Preservation	About 5 years
Access	https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu
Comments	None

2. Other Deliverables

Type	Report
Format	
Description	Technical reports of the various work packages describing the work performed and results achieved by the date of delivery
Sharing	Public (PU)
Owners	CompactLight project partners
License	CC-BY
Reuse	The deliverables describe in detail the work and the achieved results in the different work packages in detail and create therefore the basis for any future activity for the further the development of the technologies and their use in application projects
Archiving	All CompactLight deliverables have been archived in the CompactLight Community in Zenodo, including standard metadata
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in Zenodo
Access	https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu ; corresponding authors
Comments	A complete list of all deliverables accepted by the end of 2021 can be found in the Annex of the CompactLight CDR and on the project's website

3. Scientific Publications

Type	Scientific articles
Format	
Description	Scientific papers describing the work performed and the results achieved by the project
Sharing	Open access
Owners	Authors of the publications
License	CC-BY
Reuse	The publications describe the work and the achieved results in detail and can be used by other researchers in the field for further scientific activities based on the published project results
Archiving	All CompactLight publications have been archived in the CompactLight Community in Zenodo, including standard metadata
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in Zenodo
Access	https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage
Information	Corresponding authors of the publications
Comments	A complete list of all publications published by the end of 2021 can be found in the Annex of the CompactLight CDR and on the project's website

4. Design parameters

Type	Data files
Format	, spreadsheet
Description	Detailed parameters of the CompactLight design collected in the CompactLight Parameter List
Sharing	Open access
Owners	CompactLight project partners
License	CC-BY
Reuse	The data can be reused to understand the CompactLight design in more detail and to develop concrete design studies for facilities based on the CompactLight technologies; the CompactLight Parameter List can also be used as a template for parameter lists in general
Archiving	The CompactLight Parameter List is included in format in the CompactLight CDR and in D7.2, which will both be archived in the CompactLight Community in Zenodo after acceptance by the European Commission; a spreadsheet version for easy reuse will be attached as an open data file in spreadsheet format for easy reuse
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in Zenodo
Access	https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu
Comments	The CompactLight parameter list will also be available on the project's website

5. Simulation Data

Type	Data files
Format	Specific formats
Description	Input and output data of the simulations performed for the CompactLight design study
Sharing	Partly open access, partly restricted access
Owners	Project partners that have performed the design studies; CompactLight partners
License	Open data: CC-BY; others: as indicated by the owners
Reuse	The data will be reused by the CompactLight partners for further development activities; they can be used by interested applicants as starting point for their own design studies; upon request and agreement with the project partners
Archiving	The simulation data are archived in the CompactLight GIT space
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in GIT
Access	https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage https://gitlab.cern.ch/XLS-Git
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu ; owners of the data
Comments	None

6. Cost Analysis Data

Type	Data files
Format	pdf, spreadsheet
Description	Input data and output data of the CompactLight cost analysis; the data have been organized by means of a costing tool that was originally developed to estimate the CLIC project cost at CERN. The tool provides the interface to a large database where the information is stored and secured. The CERN Advanced Information Systems team (AIS) has provided a dedicated interface specifically prepared for the CompactLight project.
Sharing	Open access (on request)
Owners	Project partners involved in the cost analysis; CompactLight partners
License	CC-BY
Reuse	The data can be used by interested applicants as the basis for the cost analysis of their own projects and by the CompactLight partners for updates based on further development activities
Archiving	Core results of the cost analysis are published in the CompactLight CDR and D7.2 in format; these documents will be archived in Zenodo and on the project's website. The input data are stored in the CERN Advanced Information Systems AIS
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in Zenodo and in the CERN AIS
Access	Publications on cost analysis results: https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage Cost analysis input data: The database of the cost analysis data will remain accessible for consultation in a simplified form upon request by interested users, see contact information below
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu ; corresponding authors; owners of the data
Comments	None

7. Landscape Analysis Data

Type	Statistical data
Format	, spreadsheet
Description	Community, facility and user data collected as an input to the landscape analysis
Sharing	Open access
Owners	Project partners involved in the cost analysis; CompactLight partners
License	CC-0
Reuse	The data can be reused for further investigations into the topic, in particular for long term trend and community analyses; they will be reused by the CompactLight partners for this purpose and can be useful for accompanying strategic documents of re-search infrastructure projects
Archiving	Data will be attached as data files in spreadsheet format to all relevant CompactLight publications (CompactLight CDR, D7.2, scientific papers on these results) and archived in the Compact-Light Community in Zenodo
Preservation	Long-term preservation is ensured in Zenodo
Access	https://www.zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CompactLight https://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu ; corresponding authors
Comments	None

8. Software

Type	Computer codes
Format	Specific programming languages
Description	Computer codes developed / further developed by the partners for the simulations required in the course of the study
Sharing	Confidential
Owners	Authors of the codes
License	Trade Secret
Reuse	The software will be used at the moment by the owners for further R&D activities; it might become open later on
Archiving	By authors
Preservation	By authors
Access	Potentially through collaborations with the authors, depends on the single case
Information	compactlight@elettra.eu ; corresponding authors
Comments	None
